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An Optimized Sliding Mode Control For Gantry Crane System Based On Graylag Goose Optimization Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

This research proposes the development of a sliding mode controller with Graylag Goose Optimization (GGO) Scheme for stabilization in Gantry Crane System (GCS). Gantry crane is a type of overhead crane with single or double girder configuration supported by freestanding legs that move on a wheel or along track or rail system. Gantry cranes have applications in mining, steel mills, ports, special construction sites, assembly lines and factory for transporting heavy loads. Inertia forces due to prescribed motion of the payload and excitation of the base due to motions in the supporting mechanism of the crane, external disturbance such as wind could result in unwanted motions of the crane. These factors generate swinging of the load during the transportation process. Existing nonlinear controllers show a good system performance when compared with linear controllers whose performance deteriorate with increase in operation range and uncertainty, hence the need for nonlinear controller that will guarantee system performance in presence of uncertainty. The Sliding Mode Controller (SMC) is one the nonlinear controller used on this system because of its robustness. However the gains of the controller are to be tuned for efficient control of the system. Metaheuristic algorithms have been successfully utilized for obtaining the optimal gains of the controller. The GGO has been successful in addressing optimization and engineering problems, like other metaheuristic algorithms but faces a common challenge of getting stuck in local minima while attempting to achieve rapid convergence. To achieve this, the Sliding Mode Controller (SMC) augmented with Graylag Goose Optimization (GGO) Scheme for stabilization in Gantry Crane System (GCS) was developed. Modeling and simulation of the GCS with the developed controller was carried out using MATLAB/Simulink R2022b. Performance of the GCS with the developed GGO-SMC controller was evaluated based on steady state error, overshoot and settling time as performance metrics and the results were compared with conventional SMC controller as reported in literature. The developed GGO-SMC outperformed conventional SMC controller in terms of system stabilization. There was 44.20% improvement in settling time, 82.50% improvement in overshoot and 98.99% improvement in steady state error in terms of cart position and swing angle.

Keywords: Sliding Mode Control, Graylag Goose Optimization (GGO), Scheme for stabilization in Gantry Crane System (GCS), Gantry Crane System

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Crane is a machine or device used by human to help humans to move loads, or better known as payload, from one point to another. A crane is typically equipped with a hoist or wire rope drum, wire ropes or chains and sheaves that can be used to lift or lower the load or move the load horizontally. The hoist functions as a simple machine which helps human to move loads beyond the capability of a human. There are many types of crane, which are named based on their application: automatic crane, cab-operated crane, cantilever gantry crane, floor-operated crane, boom crane, rotary crane, gantry crane, jib crane, mobile crane, overhead traveling crane, power-operated crane, pulpit-operated crane, remote-operated crane, semi gantry crane, wall-mounted crane and wall-mounted jib crane.

In the transportation and construction companies, crane systems are rapidly deployed to ease the transportation of heavy loads. Cranes are a crucial part of the industrial machinery system because, they are used to carry out transportation of heavy machines or goods from one point to another. However, in the process of transporting such loads, load swinging occurs as a result of acceleration or deceleration of the crane which tend to affect the positioning precision of the load (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2018). Payload pendulation and load position precision are two important aspects of the crane system. Undesirable crane motions or disturbances such as load bouncing, twisting, and swinging coupled with external disturbance such as wind are common during load hoisting operation. The performance and productivity of the system is affected drastically due to the presence of this unwanted motions, as they affect precise positioning of the payload (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2018). Accidents and damages to buildings or facilities that are close to crane could occurred due to the swinging or pendulation of the payload (Yoon *et al.*, 2014). Rapid application of crane system for lifting and loads transportation in industries and ports leads to evolvement of high-speed operating cranes. This fast speed operation in absent of control system lead to presence of high load swing, resulting in creating a danger zone by causing damage to equipment, facilities and structures around the crane and tend to affect the precision in load positioning (Kim *et al.*, 2014; Le *et al.*, 2014).

Efficient controllers that will guarantee safety and performance are important due to the fact that, these cranes are increasingly bigger and faster (Abdel-Rahman *et al.*, 2003). The crane system is a special case of control system (termed under actuated) in which the number of control variables is higher than the input variables, fewer inputs are used to control many outputs (Biao, L. *et al.*, 2018; Renuka & Mathew, 2013). The area of application of the crane system at times can influence the management of the payload swing. In some aspects, during payload transportation, large pendulation of the load is allowed during travelling stage as long as residual pendulation at the destination point is insignificant to prevent accurate load positioning (Abdel-Rahman *et al.*, 2003). In cluttered workspace like nuclear reactor zones, almost zero pendulation or swing of the load is expected during travelling stage and at load destination by imposing stiffed conditions on swing suppression.

Inertia forces due to prescribed motion of the payload and excitation of the base as a result of motions in the supporting mechanism of the crane could result in these unwanted motions of the crane. An earlier technique employed by crane operators was to perform load maneuvering slowly or stop the operation in order to dampen out motion of the payload when such occurred. Such operations introduced time delay, reduced crane efficiency and increased operating cost hence the need for automatic control (Abdel-Rahman *et al.*, 2003). In the process of designing controller for a crane system, almost all the design decisions use to be a trade-off between having the load transported as fast as possible or having a safe (i.e. less load swing) transportation (Pauluk, 2016). Several conceptual and constructive control methods had been applied in the stabilization and adaptive control of nonlinear systems such as the crane, and most of these methods rely on application of energy (Lyapunov) function to the construction of the control law or in close loop analysis of the system (Astolfi & Ortega, 2003).

The Sliding Mode Control (SMC) is a robust nonlinear control technique due to its insensitivity to system uncertainty that has been applied for the stabilization of Gantry Crane System (GCS). This work employs the Graylag Goose Optimization (GGO) technique to tune the gains of the SMC in order to have a better performance of the GCS when compared with the conventional tuning

2.0 Problem Statement/Justification

Load swing is a common problem during crane operation, and this may lead to instability and poor load positioning. Several control techniques among which include Input shapers, Command smoothing, Filter, PID, LQR, State feedback Controller, Fuzzy Logic, Neural Network, the time-optimal classical control, hybrid fuzzy-PID, Adaptive Control, SMC had been applied for crane stabilization. Nevertheless, the presence of external disturbances and uncertainty during crane operation limits the efficiency of these methods thus making it difficult to achieved stabilization and set-point tracking in the gantry crane system. However, good control of disturbances can allow for compensation of these negative effects, thereby enhancing the robustness of the system when subjected to disturbance. The SMC technique is a robust nonlinear controller which had been applied for stabilization and position control of GCS. However the gains of the controllers ought to be tuned appropriately to obtain the optimal gains for efficient control of the system. The GGO as a metaheuristic algorithm has been proven to be efficient in solving optimization problem due its fast convergence. Therefore this research proposes a sliding mode controller augmented with GGO Scheme for stabilization and tracking of load position coordinates in the gantry crane system. The controller, if developed and applied on the system will guarantee stability and robustness against uncertainty because it had proved to be a promising tool in nonlinear systems stabilization.

3.0 Objectives of the Study

The aim of this research is to develop a sliding mode controller augmented with GGO Scheme for stabilization and tracking of load position coordinates in the gantry crane system.

The followings are the objectives of the research:

1. To develop the Simulink model of the GCS in MATLAB/Simulink based on the mathematical model reported in the work of (Buhari *et al.*, 2022) to be used for simulation and controller development throughout the studies.
2. To develop the sliding mode controller (SMC) for stabilization and tracking of the position of the load of the developed GCS model in (1) and to optimize the gains parameters of the developed controller based on (GGO).
3. To compare the GCS performance using the developed GGO-SMC and the SMC scheme under different external disturbance levels

4.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Renuka and Mathew (2013) analyzed the performance of proportional-integral-differential (PID) controller on different models of crane system. Two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) models were considered with inclusion of cable hoisting, frictional force and wind disturbance dynamics. Simulation and analysis were done on the system and it was observed that the complex nature of the system reduced the performance of the controller with present of oscillation in the swing angle, trolley displacement and cable hoisting. In conclusion, it was found out that there is compromise between having a precise load positioning control and reduction in load swing, hence the need for a controller that will guarantee both precision positioning and load swing reduction.

Khan (2013) proposed a nonlinear robust controller for an elastic drive system using a two-mass-model of a milling machine. The controller design is based on Immersion and Invariance technique and it is used to achieve position control and suppression of vibration in the two-mass model milling system. The developed control methodology was simulated and transient analysis was carried out and the result is compared with that of other control techniques (i.e. PID) and input/output feedback linearization) where the proposed controller showed better performance in terms of transient stability, robustness to parameter variation and external disturbance.

Li *et al.*, (2013) presented a controller for stabilization of an aircraft wing rock system. The stabilizing controller is designed based on immersion and invariance design concept and the control objective is to have all the system states regulated to zero equilibrium point. In this regard, the controller was simulated and its performance was compared to backstepping control technique where the proposed IIC

outperformed the backstepping controller in terms of the faster convergence of the system states to the zero equilibrium.

Kanchanaharuthai (2014) proposed a nonlinear IIC for transient stability, and enhancement of voltage and frequency regulation in excitation and Static Var Compensator of an electrical power system. The controller was able to achieve a better power angle stability, voltage and frequency regulation. Additionally, the transient close loop system is asymptotically stable with the application of the proposed controller. The system is simulated and the result is compared with other control techniques i.e. passivation technique and feedback linearization where the proposed controller outperformed the other two controllers in terms of percentage overshoot and settling time.

Pauluk (2016) present a time-optimal linear quadratic controller for swing reduction in 3D crane. Supervision of the control process and elimination of the undesired features of the optimal trajectory is done by the linear quadratic (LQ) controller that also ensured robustness of the controller with respect to nonlinear models by using the idea of neighboring optimal trajectories. Results from simulations and experiments showed the presented control was able to reduced swinging of the load by 25% and 35% in x and z-directions respectively. This is an improvement over previously proposed optimal control techniques but with present of oscillations after some times, hence the room for further research.

Nguyen *et al*, (2017) proposed adaptive sliding mode controller (SMC) based on radial basis function (RBF) network for overhead crane. The SMC is used to suppress load swinging and achieved load positioning precision. The RBF network is used to compensate the uncertain nonlinear function contained in the SMC control law. In other to have a stable control, an adaptive tuning algorithm was added to tune gain parameters of the classical SMC. Results of the proposed control system was compared to that of classical SMC technique and the proposed outperformed the classical controller in terms of parametric variation and robustness to disturbance but with the present of oscillation. Residual oscillations of the payload make it an open area for further research to obtain a controller that will further suppress the swinging of the load.

He *et al*, (2017) proposed barrier-Lyapunov function (BLF)-based controller for boundary vibration control of 2D crane with output constraint. Active vibration control laws were constructed using Lyapunov energy function one to take care of the longitudinal vibration in the hoisting cable while the other takes care of the transverse vibration of the hoisting cable all in order to suppress the swinging of the payload within a set boundary condition. Thus, the controller was able to achieved the set objective but this control is only for a particular work environment. Hence the need for a generalized control system.

Chwa (2017) proposed a nonlinear anti-swing controller based on SMC. The work considered a 3D model of the crane system that include movement of the trolley, girder, and payload swing. The SMC controller was able to reduced the payload swing and track the desired position of the load, but with present of oscillation even after a particular duration of time and chattering of the control signal. The work reported that, the chattering in the control signal can be taken care of but at the expense of robustness of the controller, hence the need for a nonlinear controller that will guarantee fast swing reduction and improve productivity of the system.

Naskar and Pal (2017) proposed a self-tuning fuzzy-proportional-differential (PD) controller for payload swing reduction and precise load positioning in crane system. The fuzzy logic algorithm is used to tune the parameters of the PD controller. In order to achieve the tuning task, a type-1 fuzzy logic is use to tune type-2 fuzzy logic that formed the self-tuning fuzzy logic. This control technique proved to be successful in reducing payload swing and achieving load positioning at the desired position when compared to the existing conventional methods (T1FLPDC, T2FLPDC and T1STFLDDC). This method gave improved result with regards to swing reduction and load position, but there is no standard tool for tuning the type-2 fuzzy logic, hence the need for a standard control technique.

Liu *et al*, (2018) developed a modified fuzzy-PID controller for minimization of harsh sea conditions on salvage crane. Wave compensator algorithm which is an improved version of the traditional fuzzy-PID algorithm due to modification of the fuzzy aspects (rules, inputs and output). The E and EC rules are used simultaneously to update the PID parameters and these rules were reduced from the usual 49 rules to 14

rules, fewer reasoning items were obtained in order to have less reasoning time and fast controller response. This result in better performance of the system with the improved fuzzy-PID controller when compared to the traditional fuzzy-PID in terms of disturbance rejection and system stability. Thus, the controller did better when compared to the existing ones in literatures but there is still need for a controller that is simpler, and takes into account system states for better stabilization and improved efficiency.

Lu Biao *et al.*, (2018) developed a model of dual gantry crane and proposed a nonlinear controller for stabilization of the crane system. Lyapunov function and Lasalle theorem were used to design the control law. Stability analysis and simulations results showed the proposed controller was able to stabilized the system at desired equilibrium point. The control scheme was compared to that of LQR, PID and independent control methods in which the proposed outperformed the other three controllers in terms of reduction in load swing and position tracking.

Abdullahi *et al.*, (2018) proposed an adaptive output-based command shaping control technique for swing reduction in overhead crane system. The work considered a model that includes cable hoisting, variable payload mass and wind disturbance to the system. The controller is design by selecting a reference model that best described the desired system and connect it in forward loop with the actual system, while the controller is place in series with the actual system with it output signal being an input to the system. In this control technique, the poles of the actual system were replaced with poles of the reference model by the zeros of the controller. Simulations of the system was carried out with the results compared with that of existing controllers (i.e. extra insensitive (EI) and zero-vibration-derivative-derivative control (ZVDD)) in which the proposed outperformed the other two input shaper controllers in terms of disturbance rejection and load swing reduction. Thus, the controller performed well but there is present of oscillation at the output of the system and it is valid for small operation range, hence the need for nonlinear controller that will guarantee stability even with wide operation time.

5.0 METHODOLOGY

To achieve the set objectives of the research, the methodology adopted were analyzed as follows:

5.1 Modeling of the GCS based on the mathematical model of GCS dynamics

The mathematical model of the GCS presented in equations (1) to (14) defined was modelled in Simulink to obtain the GCS model $\{\dot{x}=X_1, \dot{x}=X_2, \dot{\theta}=X_3$ and $\theta=X_4\}$. This model uses the front wheels for steering control and the back wheels for speed control

Figure 1: Model of a Gantry Set-up (Hussein *et al.*, 2020)

The set-up of a gantry crane is given in Figure 2.3, where x is the displacement of the trolley, θ is the angular displacement of the payload from the vertical position, U_1 and U_2 is the control inputs, L is the length of the hoisting cable, m is mass of the payload, M is mass of the trolley, and g is acceleration due to gravity acting on the payload.

The dynamic model of overhead crane system can be acquired using the Euler-Lagrange approach given below. (Hussein *et al.*, 2022)

$$\text{Kinetic energy of the trolley } (T_1) = \frac{1}{2}M\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Kinetic energy of the payload

$$(T_2) = \frac{1}{2}m\left[\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 + L^2\left(\frac{d\theta}{dt}\right)^2 + 2\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)\left(\frac{d\theta}{dt}\right)L\cos\theta\right] \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Total Kinetic energy}(T) = T_1 + T_2 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Total Potential energy } (P) = -mgL\sin\theta \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Using Lagrange's Equation, } \frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}}\right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial q} = Q \quad (5)$$

$$L = T - P \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}M\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}m\left[\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 + L^2\left(\frac{d\theta}{dt}\right)^2 + 2\left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)\left(\frac{d\theta}{dt}\right)L\cos\theta\right] + mgL\sin\theta = F \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the non-linear model of GCS can be summarized by resolving equation (7) into two components, F_x = direction of trolley and F_L = direction of the payload

$$(M + m) \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + mL\cos\theta \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} - mL\sin\theta \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt}\right)^2 = U_1 + U_2 \quad (8)$$

$$mL\cos\theta \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + mL^2 \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + mgL\sin\theta = 0 \quad (9)$$

Where; M is mass of the cart in (Kg), m represent mass of the payload, L is length of the hoisting (suspension) cable, g acceleration due to gravity, u is the applied control force or torque, x is displacement of the trolley or distance travelled by the trolley and θ is the swing angle of the payload.

Consequently, Equation (8) & (9) can be expressed in matrix form ;

$$\begin{bmatrix} M + m & mL\cos\theta \\ mL\cos\theta & mL^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} mL\dot{\theta}^2 \sin\theta \\ -mgL\sin\theta \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} (u_1 + u_2) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{K_{22}f_a - K_{12}f_u}{K_{11}K_{22} - K_{12}K_{21}} + \frac{K_{22}}{K_{11}K_{22} - K_{12}K_{21}} (u_1 + u_2) \quad (11)$$

$$\ddot{\theta} = \frac{-K_{21}f_a + K_{11}f_u}{K_{11}K_{22} - K_{12}K_{21}} + \frac{-K_{21}}{K_{11}K_{22} - K_{12}K_{21}} (u_1 + u_2) \quad (12)$$

The equation (11) and (12) can be written as follows:

$$\ddot{x} = f_{11} + b_{11}(u_1 + u_2) \quad (13)$$

$$\ddot{\theta} = f_{12} + b_{12}(u_1 + u_2) \quad (14)$$

5.2 Development of a sliding mode controller (SMC) for stabilization and tracking.

The sliding mode function can be defined as:

$$S_1 = \dot{x} + d_1x + k_1\dot{\theta} + k_2\theta \quad (15)$$

$$S_2 = \dot{x} + d_3x + k_3\dot{\theta} + k_4\theta \quad (16)$$

By differentiating equation (11) and (12) while substituting equations (13) and (14)

$$\dot{S}_1 = f_{11} + k_1f_{12} + (b_{11} + c_2b_{22})u_1 + d_1\dot{x} + k_2\dot{\theta} \quad (17)$$

$$\dot{S}_2 = f_{11} + k_3f_{12} + (b_{11} + c_2b_{22})u_2 + d_3\dot{x} + k_4\dot{\theta} \quad (18)$$

The control law (U_1+U_2) can be express

$$U_1 = -\frac{1}{b_{11}+c_2b_{22}} [f_{11} + k_1f_{12} + d_1\dot{x} + k_2\dot{\theta} + \zeta \text{sgn}(S_1)] \quad (19)$$

$$U_2 = -\frac{1}{b_{11}+c_2b_{22}} [f_{11} + k_3f_{12} + d_3\dot{x} + k_4\dot{\theta} + \zeta \text{sgn}(S_2)] \quad (20)$$

As seen in the equation (19) and (20), the controller gains parameters are d_1, k_1, k_2, d_3, k_3 and k_4 . The gains parameters have a direct impact on the system control law (U_1+U_2). The greater the values of d_1, k_1, k_2, d_3, k_3 and k_4 . the faster the system approached the sliding surface. Hence, control law (U_1+U_2) depends on values of the gains parameters, d_1, k_1, k_2, d_3, k_3 and k_4 . Therefore, there is need to employ an optimization algorithm to search for the optimal value of d_1, k_1, k_2, d_3, k_3 and k_4 .

In this research, Greylag Goose Optimization technique will be adopted and the objective function will be the root mean square error (RMSE) of the control input (U_1+U_2). GGO-SMC was developed for control of GCS. The Simulink model of the GCS was developed first and then the optimize GGO-SMC scheme. The developed GGO-SMC scheme is expected to control the position and swing angle of the GCS.

5.3 Formulation of optimization problem based on the Parameters

To obtain an optimized weigh for the controller input, the weighting factor is given in the equation (21) was formulated into an objective function using the control law in equation (19) and (20).The objective of the optimization problem is to minimize the weight by optimizing the weighting factor d_1 , k_1 , k_2 , d_3 , k_3 , and k_4 for root mean square error minimization between the control inputs (u_1 and u_2) and their reference values (u_{ref}). The objective function is given as

$$F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{U_{1i} - U_{ref}}{U_{1i}} \right)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{U_{2i} - U_{ref}}{U_{2i}} \right)^2} \quad (21)$$

The boundaries for the system variables were determined by considering the range derived from the implementation of SMC without utilizing GGO. The optimum solution is determined subject to the constraints:

$$4 < d_1 < 6 \quad (22)$$

$$1 < k_1 < 2 \quad (23)$$

$$1 < k_2 < 2 \quad (24)$$

$$4 < d_3 < 6 \quad (25)$$

$$1.5 < k_3 < 2 \quad (26)$$

$$1 < k_4 < 2 \quad (27)$$

Therefore, k_1 , k_2 , k_3 , k_4 , d_1 and d_3 are the parameters of the weighting factor that must be optimized in order to achieve the objective function. The GGO algorithm was employed in this research to optimize the cost function parameters. Equation (21) serves as evaluation criteria for the optimality of the results obtained by GGO.

6.0 Simulation Results

The results are expected to outperform the work of Hussein et al., (2020). The simulation results obtained based on the methodologies presented in chapter three that addressed the research objectives are discussed compared with the work of (Hussein et al., 2020) are presented in this section.

6.1 Convergence of GGO algorithm

In this section the convergence of the Smell agent optimization is discussed. As GGO was used in obtaining best SMC parameters of the given cost function, the convergence graph of simulation on benchmark model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: GGO Convergence Plot on Benchmark System

Figure 2 shows the GGO convergence on the benchmark model. It can be observed that the best convergence accuracy occurred at, converging at the 3rd iteration with an optimized cost function. The SMC was tuned to search for best gains using GGO, after running 50 iterations, the best parameters were found as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of Best Smell Object

GGO Parameters	Value
Cost Function	1.61473904073533e+06
d ₁	4.877
K ₁	1.4463
K ₂	2.8329
d ₃	4.4193
K ₃	1.7402
K ₄	1.113

6.2 Stabilization Results

The results of the stabilization of the system using the developed GGO sliding mode controller under different initial conditions (ICs) of $[0.98, 0.2, \frac{\pi}{16}, \frac{\pi}{8}]$ and $[0.5, 1.2, \frac{\pi}{8}, \frac{\pi}{4}]$ which represent position of the system states were given in the results presented in the Figure 3 to Figure 7

Figure 3: Linear Displacement of the Cart

From the analysis of Figure 3, it can be seen that there was a sharp rise in amplitude of trolley position of the GCS when an input signal was applied to the system when using SMC. However, when using the GGO-SMC was reduced and the controller was able to stabilize it faster to zero equilibrium point and the oscillation was less when compared to the existing scheme using SMC. It implies that the controllability of linear displacement state. This shows that the GGO-SMC provides an improved dynamic stability for the GCS during operation.

Figure 4: Linear Speed of the Cart

In Figure 4, it was observed that linear speed of the cart using SAO-SMC controller was having a longer amplitude at initial point, but later stabilized to zero equilibrium point when the controller acted based on the error signal generated. However, using GGO-SMC, the amplitude of the trolley settles faster to the equilibrium position showing improvement over SMC.

Figure 5: Load Swing Angle

Figure 5 shows the load swing angle of the GCS. From the figure above, it was observed that using the SMC, the swing angle takes longer time to stabilize to the equilibrium point. However, using GGO-SMC, the swing angle stabilize faster to the equilibrium point which implies the system is state controllable.

Figure 6: Load Angular Speed

Figure 6 shows the angular velocity of the GCS. From the figure above, it was observed that the angular velocity using the developed GGO-SMC, there is a rise in amplitude due to transient nature of the system, but it later converges faster to the equilibrium. Using controller-based SMC, there is a sharp rise in amplitude, which occurred due to transient nature of the system but it took a longer time to stabilized and converged to the equilibrium.

The controller response for system stabilization under the first given initial conditions is given in Figure 7

Figure 7: Stabilizing Control Action

Figure 7 shows control action $u(t)$ that stabilized the states of the GCS under the given initial conditions stated early. It was observed that, amplitude of the control action of the SMC was large at some point due to the sharp rise in the system state compared to GGO-SMC. But later the GGO-SMC settles at zero before GGO-SMC controller when the states stabilized at the desire equilibrium. Control input of the SMC without GGO shows rapid changes which is dangerous in case of practical application. Moreover, the developed controller with GGO requires less amount of control effort as compared to SMC without GGO.

7.0 CONCLUSION

This research has presented the development of a sliding mode controller augmented with GGO Scheme for stabilization and tracking of load position coordinates in the gantry crane system (GCS). The model of the GCS was developed in Simulink. Subsequently, an optimal control approach using SMC and GGO based on the formulated objective function was developed. The simulation was carried out in MATLAB/Simulink 2022b. The performance evaluation of the results was carried out and compared to the GCS developed by (Hussein *et al.*, 2022) in terms of settling time, overshoot and steady state error. The simulation results reveal better performance of the developed controller when compared to controller presented in (Hussein *et al.*, 2020) with 42.20% improvement in settling time in terms of load swing. While this work report 82.50% improvement in overshoot of load swing respectively. Additionally, it showed 98.99% improvement in steady state error with respect load swing. Hence, a solution to problems of load swing and precise load positioning in crane operation is presented.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, A. M., Mohamed, Z., Selamat, H., Pota, H. R., Abidin, M. Z., Ismail, F., . . . Processing, S. (2018). Adaptive output-based command shaping for sway control of a 3D overhead crane with payload hoisting and wind disturbance. *98*, 157-172.
- Abdel-Rahman, E. M., Nayfeh, A. H., & Masoud, Z. N. J. M. A. (2003). Dynamics and control of cranes: A review. *Journal of Vibration and Control*, *9*(7), 863-908. doi: DOI: 10.1177/1077546303009007007
- Astolfi, A., & Ortega, R. J. I. T. o. A. c. (2003). Immersion and invariance: a new tool for stabilization and adaptive control of nonlinear systems. *48*(4), 590-606
- Chwa, D. J. I. T. o. I. E. (2017). Sliding-Mode-Control-Based Robust Finite-Time Antisway Tracking Control of 3-D Overhead Cranes. *64*(8), 6775-6784.
- He, X., Shi, J., He, W., & Sun, C. J. I.-P. (2017). Boundary vibration control of a variable length crane system in two dimensional space with output constraints. *50*(1), 11996-12001
- Kanchanaharuthai, A. J. M. P. i. E. (2014). Immersion and invariance-based coordinated generator excitation and SVC control for power systems. *2014*, 11. doi: 10.1155/2014/720570
- Kim, J.-J., Lee, S.-G., Lim, T.-G., Nho, L. C. J. I. j. o. p. e., & manufacturing. (2014). Second-order sliding mode control of a 3D overhead crane with uncertain system parameters. *15*(5), 811-819
- Li, S., Liu, X., Dong, X., Jing, Y., Liu, X. J. I. J. o. I. C., Information, & Control. (2013). A novel controller for a class of nonlinear systems via immersion and invariance. *9*(8), 3463-3470.
- Khan, I. U. (2013). *Robust control of elastic drive systems using the immersion and invariance methodology*
- Lu Biao, Fang Yongchun, & Ning, S. (2018). Modeling and nonlinear coordination control for an underactuated dual overhead crane system. *Automatica*, *91*, 244-255
- Liu, X., Li, W., Wang, W., & Xu, Z. J. A. J. o. C. (2018). Control for the New Harsh sea Conditions Salvage Crane Based on Modified Fuzzy PID.
- Naskar, I., & Pal, A. (2017). *Type-2 Fuzzy Controller with Type-1 Tuning Scheme for Overhead Crane Control*. Paper presented at the International Conference on Computational Intelligence, Communications, and Business Analytics
- Nguyen, N. P., Ngo, Q. H., & Nguyen, C. N. (2017). *Adaptive sliding mode control using radial basis function network for container cranes*. Paper presented at the Control, Automation and Systems (ICCAS), 2017 17th International Conference on
- Pauluk, M. J. P. E. (2016). Optimal and robust control of 3D crane. *92*(2), 206--212.
- Renuka, V., & Mathew, A. T. J. I. J. T. A. R. M. E. (2013). Precise Modelling of a Gantry Crane System Including Friction 3D Angular Swing and Hoisting Cable Flexibility. *2*, 119-125.
- Yoon, J., Nation, S., Singhose, W., & Vaughan, J. E. J. I. T. o. C. S. T. (2014). Control of crane payloads that bounce during hoisting. *22*(3), 1233-1238